

INTERNATIONAL STUDENT CONGRESS

ABSTRACT BOOK

2025

Dear Participants,

A congress strongly depends on its passionate participants presenting their research, critically discussing everything with each other and of course learning from and with each other throughout a great variety of workshops and social events. Once again, this year, with over 160 attendees from more than 30 countries, we were able to achieve this and broaden the horizons of our knowledge, particularly focusing on the highly exciting field of pediatric medicine. For this, as the president of the 11th International Student Congress 2025, I want to deeply thank you for sharing your time with us during these couple of days at the Medical University of Graz.

I want to thank Prof. Nassim Ghaffari Tabrizi for her great and on-going support of our congress. Without her the art exhibition and the donations to the Styrian cancer aid would just be impossible to accomplish. Also, I want to thank Prof. Sandra Johanna Holasek, for her great support and the opportunity to invite us into the Styrian parliament. All our countries strongly depend on such exchanges, making social events like this very important. Finally, our gratitude to the president of the Medical University of Graz, Prof. Andrea Kurz, for taking her time despite her full schedule and participating in our congress, meeting with everybody and joining our discussions throughout the congress.

Finally, my biggest respects to my team of this year's congress. Without their willingness to accomplish this and their passion for what we achieved the congress would not be what it is supposed to be.

In conclusion, we hope you had an enriching time in Graz and achieved what you wanted to achieve during those days. Hopefully we can welcome everybody from all around the world very soon again for the 12th International Student Congress.

Stay tuned!

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "A. Abedini". The signature is written in a cursive style and is underlined with a single horizontal line.

Ashkan Abedini

President of the 11th International Student Congress 2025

Pineal Gland Volume Loss In Oncology Patients: Association With Chemotherapy Duration

M. Šarošković¹, M. Vuković^{1,2}, J. Vasić¹

¹Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia;

²Department for radiology diagnostics, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

Introduction:The pineal gland is a neuroendocrine structure whose function can be disrupted in patients with malignancies.

Aim:This study examines the differences in pineal gland volume between oncology patients and healthy controls, as well as the relationship between volume and the duration of chemotherapy.

Material and Methods:A retrospective study included 400 participants, divided into two groups: 200 oncology patients and 200 healthy controls. The pineal gland volume was measured using MRI scans, utilizing T1-sagittal, T2-coronal/axial sections, and post-contrast 3D T1W MPRAGE tomograms. The volume was calculated based on the ellipse approximation formula: $V = (L \times H \times W)/2$. The study analyzed the relationships between pineal gland volume and factors such as age, sex, primary tumor origin, and the duration of chemotherapy.

Results:The pineal gland volume was significantly smaller in oncology patients in comparison with the healthy controls ($p < 0.001$). The average volume in oncology patients was $32.41 \pm 16.79 \text{ mm}^3$, whereas in healthy controls, it was $59.26 \pm 29.99 \text{ mm}^3$. A significant volume loss was observed in patients with malignancies, regardless of sex, with no notable differences between groups. Age also did not significantly influence gland volume ($p > 0.05$). The primary tumor site did not have significantly influence gland volume ($p > 0.05$). A moderate positive correlation was observed between the duration of chemotherapy and pineal gland volume ($\rho = 0.322$; $p = 0.007$).

Discussion:The pineal gland showed smaller volume in oncology patients compared to the healthy controls, while the increase in volume following prolonged chemotherapy may reflect adaptive mechanisms or the direct effects of therapy.